

STITCHING EFFECT ON FLEXURAL AND INTERLAMINAR PROPERTIES OF MWK TEXTILE COMPOSITES

J-H Byun¹, C-H Lee¹, S-W Song¹, S-K Lee¹, B-S Kim¹ and C.R Joe²

¹ *Composite Materials Lab, Korea Institute of Machinery & Materials,
66 Sangnam-dong, Changwon, Kyungnam, 641-010, South Korea*

² *Department of Mechanical Design and Manufacturing Engineering
Changwon National University
9 Sarim-dong, Changwon, Kyungnam, 641-773, South Korea*

SUMMARY: The stitching process has been widely utilized for the improvement of through-thickness property of the conventional laminated composites. This paper reports the effects of stitching on the flexural and interlaminar shear properties of multi-axial warp knitted composites in order to identify the mechanical property improvements. Considered parameters are as follows: the stacking regularity of the multi-axial warp knits, the stitch spacings, the stitching types, the stitching location, and the location of compression fixture nose. These parameters have little effect on the flexural and interlaminar shear properties, except for the case of stitching location. Stitching on the 0° fibers showed the lowest flexural strength and modulus (12% reduction for both properties). The stitch spacing of 5mm resulted in 8% reduction for the case of interlaminar strength compared with that of 10mm spacing.

KEYWORDS: stitch, MWK (Multi-axial Warp Knit), flexure, interlaminar, stacking, stitch spacing, lock stitch

INTRODUCTION

MWK (Multi-axial Warp Knit) reinforcements consist of multi-directional fiber bundles held together by stitches in the thickness direction of the fabric as shown in Fig. 1. The major advantages of this textile are the straightness of fiber bundles, the possible incorporation of nonwoven fabrics, and elimination of ply-by-ply lamination. Because this type of textiles doesn't involve a yarn crimp which can be seen in woven textile, MWK is also called non-crimp fabric (NCF) [1]. All these factors of MWK can increase composite's mechanical properties and the production rate, as well. Although the whole layers of MWK are bound together by knitting yarns, the reinforcement in the thickness direction doesn't effective when they are used in composites. This is due to that polyester or polyethylene fibers are usually utilized for knitting yarns. Owing to the development of processing technology and introduction of new type of reinforcements, composites have been applied to larger structures such as boats and bridges. Structural design in these areas requires thicker sections and higher performance such as strength and damage tolerances. Since laminated composites have inherent weakness of delamination, it is crucial to develop three-dimensional preforms by providing additional reinforcements in the thickness direction [2]. One of the most effective

Fig. 1: Fabrication of MWK.

ways of delamination suppression is the stitching of several layers of fabrics. Much work have been carried out on stitched textile composites [3-8], but studies on the mechanical properties of stitched MWK composites have been very limited in spite of increasing usage of this type of textiles. In this study, various stitching parameters have been examined to identify their effectiveness on the flexural and interlaminar properties of MWK composites.

EXPERIMENTAL

Multi-axial Warp Knits

For the reinforcements, E-glass MWK textiles with layer sequence of $[0/-45/90/45]$ have been used. Another layer sequence of $[0/45/90/-45]$ has also been used together for symmetry construction of laminates. In order to differentiate the unit layer with the whole layer of MWK textiles, unit layer is termed as a 'layer', and the set of layers as a 'blanket' [1]. In this type of fiber arrangement, the width of 45° yarn is smaller than that of 0° yarn for the purpose of knitting. However, the content of yarns for 0° , $\pm 45^\circ$, and 90° directions are similar for providing quasi-isotropic property. The areal weight of MWK textiles in this study is 847g/m^2 approximately, and areal weight of individual layer of 0° , $\pm 45^\circ$, and 90° are 212g/m^2 , 212g/m^2 , and 203g/m^2 , respectively. The areal weight of stitch yarns is 8g/m^2 . It is also noted that there exists a gap between planar yarns due to the penetration of knitting yarn, and this may cause resin pocket area when composites are fabricated.

Sample Preparation and Test Methods

In order to examine the property variation of stitched composites, the stacking regularity of MWK and the stitching parameters were considered. All sample panels were fabricated by stacking five blankets of $[0/-45/90/45]$ and $[0/45/90/-45]$, symmetrically. Thus, the stacking sequence of the sample was $[0/-45/90/45]_{5s}$.

Depending upon the relative location of 0° fiber bundles from layer to layer, the regular stack and the random stack can be defined as shown in Fig. 2. In Figures 3-4, only four blankets of symmetric arrangement were shown for clarity. The colors of yarn sections indicate the different orientations of yarns in each layer. Three parameters for stitching process have been considered: stitch spacing, types, and location. The stitching pitch was fixed as 5mm, and the width between the stitch lines was varied as 5mm and 10mm. The twisted Kevlar 29 fiber was used for the stitching thread. The stitching direction was fixed in the 0° fiber direction. The stitching type can be classified as the general lock stitch, where loops are in the middle of thickness, and the modified lock stitch, where the loop locates on the surface as shown in Figs. 3 (a) and (b). Another variation of the stitch can be whether it locates on the 0° fiber bundles or on between them, as shown in Fig. 4. Table 1 summarizes the cases of stitching parameters considered in this study. After carrying out the stitching according to various

parameters, composite panels were fabricated by RTM process. As a baseline material, unstitched samples were also prepared. The resin was epoxy for all composite panels.

To identify the effects of stitching on composites properties, flexural and interlaminar shear tests were conducted based on the specifications of ASTM D790 and ASTM D2344. The cross head speeds for each test were 2.6mm/min and 1mm/min, respectively.

Fig. 2: Stacking types shown in y - z plane: (a) regular stack; (b) random stack.

Fig. 3: Stitching types shown in x - z plane: (a) general stitching; (b) modified lock stitching.

Fig. 4: Stitching locations in y - z plane: (a) on 0° fiber bundles; (b) between 0° fiber bundles.

Table 1: Cases of stitching parameters

Case	RE05	RE10	RE10-M	RE10-A	RE10-H
Stitch spacing, mm (axial, lateral)	5, 10		10, 10		
Stitch type	general lock		modified lock	general lock	
Stitch location	between axial (0°) yarns			axial yarns	between axial yarns
Loading point	Between stitch hole				On stitch hole

RESULTS

Table 2 and 3 are the summary of flexural and interlaminar test results, respectively. Numbers in the parentheses are the standard deviations. The coefficients of variation (COV) of all data except for the case of modified lock stitching (RE10-M) were less than 5%, indicating the data deviation is very small. But, specimens of RE10-M showed the highest deviation. The modified lock stitching involves proper adjustment of tension of threads that are supplied from bobbin and needle. Carrying out modified lock stitching in this study, however, tension

adjustment was not always consistent, and this might result in the difficulty in obtaining modified lock stitches on the whole area of the sample.

Table 2: Flexural test results of non-stitched and stitched samples

Case	Flexural		
	Strength (MPa)	Modulus (GPa)	
Non-stitched	RA	527 (± 13.2)	18.65 (± 0.19)
	RE	518 (± 11.9)	18.23 (± 0.21)
Stitched	RE05	524 (± 22.8)	18.70 (± 0.68)
	RE10	525 (± 19.7)	18.70 (± 0.28)
	RE10-M	510 (± 42.2)	17.30 (± 1.08)
	RE10-A	461 (± 7.63)	16.50 (± 0.42)
	RE10-H	530 (± 13.9)	18.00 (± 0.43)

Table 3: Interlaminar shear strength of non-stitched and stitched samples

Case	Interlaminar Shear Strength (MPa)	
	Non-stitched	RA
	RE	55.6 (± 1.41)
Stitched	RE05	52.9 (± 4.01)
	RE10	57.4 (± 1.13)
	RE10-M	56.5 (± 1.10)
	RE10-A	55.8 (± 2.64)
	RE10-H	55.0 (± 3.57)

Figure 5(a) and (b) show load-displacement curves of stitched (RE-10) and non-stitched (RE) specimens. All curves show non-linearity. Both curves of stitched and non-stitched specimen for each loading condition follow the similar trend with discrepancies in maximum load and displacement. Stitched sample showed higher flexural strength and modulus due to the reinforcing effect of stitching yarns. It is noted that direction of stitching yarn is along the specimen length. In the case of interlaminar test, shear stresses were dispersed due to the existence of stitching yarns, and sample endured to higher load.

Fig.5: Load-displacement curves: (a) flexural test ; (b) interlaminar test.

Effect of Stacking Type

Both the regular stacking (RE) and the random stacking (RA) of non-stitched specimen showed similar results within the standard deviation. However, flexural and interlaminar properties were consistently higher for the case of random stacking as shown in Figs. 6(a) and (b). This is due to the fact that the random stack has more uniform stress distribution in the width direction. As shown in Fig. 2, the normal stress in x-direction, and the shear stress in the z-x plane due to the bending have higher variation in y-direction for the case of regular stack compared with that of random stack.

Effect of Stitching Density

Comparing between stitched (RE05 and RE10) and un-stitched (RE) specimens for the regular stacks, the former case showed higher flexural strength and modulus. This is mainly due to the additional reinforcements by the stitch yarns located on specimen surfaces where the maximum stress locates. It is also noted that the direction of stitch yarn is the same as that of normal stress due to the bending. The difference of flexural property between RE05 and RE10 is negligible. This is because length of stitch thread on the surfaces of RE05 and RE10 are the same, and thus there is no difference for the reinforcement effect caused by the stitch thread. However, interlaminar strength of stitch spacing of 10mm was 10% higher than that of 5mm spacing. It can be stated that as the number of stitches increases the possibility of resin rich area around them becomes higher, resulting in the reduced strength. Comparing RE, RE5, and RE10, stitching with 5mm spacing gave the lowest interlaminar strength. But, when the stitch spacing increases from 5mm to 10mm, load sharing by stitch yarns compensates the negative effect due to the resin pocket. Therefore, increasing the number of stitches doesn't always result in the improvement of interlaminar strength.

Effect of Stitching Type

Referring to the stitch type, it is generally accepted that modified lock stitching is recommended in composites in order to avoid stress concentration at loops (Fig. 3 (a)). Another reason may be due to that the general lock stitch causes tension on the perform surface, resulting in the separation of fiber bundles and potential of resin pocket. The resin rich area on the composites surface is more serious when it is under the flexural loading condition. But, results in this study showed lower strength and modulus in the modified lock stitch. This is due to the loops formed on specimen surfaces that may cause stress concentration under the flexural and interlaminar shear loading conditions. However, due to the larger standard deviation for the case of modified lock stitch (Table 2), the general tendency can't be stated based upon these results.

Effect of Stitch Location

The most evident effect of stitching on the mechanical property was the stitch location where needles penetrate as shown in Fig. 6 (a). In specimens of RE10, stitch threads are located between 0° yarn bundles. For RE10-A specimens, however, stitch threads penetrate right on 0° yarn bundles, which may cause fiber misalignment due to the bundle separation and thus resin rich area is formed around the penetration point. The fiber breakage during the stitching process is also associated with strength reduction. The fiber damage in 0° fiber bundles makes it worse under the bending mode. The flexural strength and modulus of the specimen with stitch location on 0° fiber bundles were reduced by 12% compared to that of stitching between

0° fiber bundles. The resin richness and the fiber breakage of RE10-A are believed to be the reason for the lower interlaminar strength.

Effect of Loading Point

Due to the introduction of stitching threads, the unit cell of composites is larger than that of un-stitched samples. Thus, the nose point of the loading jig in the test machine may affect the flexural and interlaminar properties. Comparing the results of loading point between the stitching holes (RE10) and those of loading point on the stitching hole (RE10-H) showed that the latter case gave higher flexural strength and modulus. The reason for this can be due to that stress was absorbed by stitching threads when the compressive load was applied. Thus, specimens of RE10-H can take higher load, and flexural strength increased.

Fig. 6: (a) Flexural strength and modulus ; (b) interlaminar shear strength of un-stitched and stitched composites with various geometric and loading parameters.

CONCLUSIONS

Effects of stacking type and stitching parameters on the flexural and interlaminar properties of MWK textile composites have been identified. E-glass MWK textiles with layer sequence of [0/-45/90/45] have been used. The stacking sequence was [0/-45/90/45]_{5s}. For the stacking type, the regular stack and the random stack were considered. Three parameters for stitching process have been considered: stitching spacing, types, and location. The location of loading nose of the test jig was also examined. Most of results were close with each other within the range of standard deviation. Among other parameters, stitching on 0° fiber bundles showed the lowest flexural strength and modulus, and the reduction was 12%, respectively, compared with those of stitching between 0° fiber bundles. This is due to the fact that stitching threads penetrating right on 0° yarn bundles may separate fiber bundles and cause fiber misalignment and resin rich area around the needle penetration point. For the case of interlaminar strength, stitching density showed the greatest effect. Stitching with 10mm spacing gave the highest interlaminar strength, and the increment was 9% compared with that of 5mm spacing. The reason for this may be the less possibility of resin rich area for the case of longer spacing of stitching.

Acknowledgement

This research was supported by a grant from the Center for Advanced Materials Processing (CAMP) of the 21st Century Frontier R&D Program and National Research Laboratory funded by the Ministry of Science and Technology, Republic of Korea.

REFERENCES

1. Bibo, G.A., Hogg, P.J., and Kemp, M., "Mechanical Characterization of Glass- and Carbon-Fibre-Reinforced Composites made with Non-Crimp Fabrics," *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 57, 1997, pp. 1221-1241.
2. Byun, J-H. and Chou, T-W., Chapter 22, Vol. 1 "Mechanics of Textile Composites," *Comprehensive Composite Material*, Edited by A. Kelly and C. Zweben, Elsevier Science Publishers, Amsterdam, Netherlands, 2000, pp. 719-761.
3. Mouritz, A.P., Leong, K.H., and Herszberg, I., "A review of the effect of stitching on the in-plane mechanical properties of fibre-reinforced polymer composites," *Composites Part A* 28, 1997, pp. 979-991.
4. Mouritz, A.P. and Cox, B.N., "A mechanistic approach to the properties of stitched laminates," *Composites Part A*, 31, 2000, pp. 1-27.
5. Dransfield, K.A., Jain L.K., and Mai, Y-W., "On the effects of stitching in CFRPs- I. mode I delamination toughness," *Composites Science and Technology*, 58, 1998, pp. 815-827.
6. Sankar, B.V and Sharma S.K., "Mode II delamination toughness of stitched graphite/epoxy textile composites," *Composites Science and Technology*, 57, 1997, pp. 729-737.
7. Larsson, F., "Damage tolerance of a stitched carbon/epoxy laminates," *Composites Part A* 28, 1997, pp. 923-934.
8. Mouritz, A.P., "Ballistic impact and explosive blast resistance of stitched composites," *Composites Part B* 32, 2001, pp. 431-439.